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AN APPRAISAL OF LIBRARY INFRASTRUCTURE FOR EFFECTIVE SERVICES DELIVERY BY LIBRARY STAFFS IN UNIVERSITY LIBRARIES IN THE NORTH-WEST NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study assesses the quality of library infrastructure, for effective services delivery, in university libraries in North-West Nigeria. The objectives were to assess the current state of library infrastructure in university libraries in North-West Nigeria and evaluate the impact library infrastructure on services delivery by library staffs in university libraries under study. A survey research design was employed, using questionnaires to collect data from library staff. The findings of the study reveal that most of the libraries in the North-West the library infrastructure is inadequate, with outdated technology, insufficient space, and poor maintenance, impacting the quality of services delivery. It was reveals that while university libraries have made significant progress in providing information resources and services, challenges persist in terms of funding, and staff capacity. The study recommends increased investment in library infrastructure, staff training, and resources to enhance the quality of library services. As users face challenges in accessing information resources due to these infrastructural limitations. The study recommends investment in modernizing library infrastructure, increasing space, and improving maintenance to enhance services delivery and support academic excellence.

Keywords: Library infrastructure, library staffs, services delivery, university libraries, North-West

Introduction

University libraries play a critical role in supporting teaching, learning, and research in higher education institutions. The quality of library infrastructure, services, and resources is essential to meeting the information needs of students, faculty members, and researchers.

This study assesses the current state of library infrastructure, for effective services delivery in university libraries in Nigeria, specifically focusing on the North West region. The assessment examines the availability of library infrastructure, for effective services delivery. These libraries were chosen due to their geographical spread and significance within the zone. As academic institutions, university libraries play a vital role in supporting research, learning, and teaching. Their primary objective is to provide high-quality of library infrastructural facilities, for their educational and research pursuits (Lee & Soohyung, 2015).

The current situation of university libraries, particularly in the North West, requires an empirical investigation to determine whether they have sufficient library infrastructure, for effective services delivery to meet user demands and to assess their service delivery in a context of increasing financial constraints and technological advancements.

This study, therefore, seeks to systematically assess the library infrastructure, for effective services delivery across the North West of Nigeria. It aims to identify gaps in the provision of infrastructural facilities, understand user needs, and suggest improvements for future service delivery. The rationale for this study is based on the pressing need to evaluate the extent to which university libraries meet the evolving facilities particularly in an era of tight funding and increasing expectations for digital services. The study is guided by the Minimum Criteria and Guidelines for Academic Libraries in Nigeria (LRCN, 2014), which provide a framework for evaluating library infrastructure, for effective services delivery.

Literature Review

Numerous studies have highlighted the importance of library infrastructure and services in supporting academic excellence (Lynch, 2008; Brophy, 2005). However, university libraries in Nigeria face challenges in providing quality services due to inadequate funding (Oki, 2011) and limited staff capacity (Baro, 2010).

University libraries play a central role in supporting the educational and research objectives of their institutions by providing access to various information resources, services, and facilities. In the context of North-Western Nigeria, understanding the adequacy, relevance, and challenges associated with these libraries is critical for fostering academic and research growth. This review explores two key areas: the current state of library infrastructure in university libraries in North-West Nigeria and the impact library infrastructure on services delivery by library staffs in university libraries in North-West Nigeria.

The current state of library infrastructure in university libraries

Adequate infrastructure is a critical element in ensuring the functionality of university libraries. Facilities such as well-maintained reading rooms, computer labs, and ICT infrastructure are necessary for providing a conducive environment for study and research. Stewart and Stout (2008) highlight that user-friendly physical spaces significantly improve the usability of library resources, while IFLA (2010) underscores the importance of modern library infrastructure in facilitating academic activities.

In many universities in North-Western Nigeria, however, library facilities are often inadequate. According to Akpan and Edem (2010), many libraries in the region suffer from overcrowding, outdated equipment, and insufficient ICT infrastructure. These challenges are exacerbated by unreliable electricity supply and poor internet connectivity, which limit the usability of digital resources (Onwudinjo, 2012). As a result, students and researchers may find it difficult to access information resources or to study in a conducive environment.

The impact library infrastructure on services delivery by library staffs in university libraries

The quality of services offered by university libraries is equally important as the resources they provide. These services include reference assistance, circulation services, interlibrary loans, and digital resource management. Gupta and Jambhekar (2002) note that high-quality library services are characterized by timely, accurate, and user-friendly support systems. The interaction between library staff and users, particularly in the provision of reference services, plays a significant role in determining user satisfaction (Ogunsola & Okusaga, 2006).

In university libraries in North-Western Nigeria, however, the quality of library services is often hindered by inadequate staff training, lack of modern technology, and poor infrastructure. Omekwu and Echezona (2008) observe that many libraries in the region have not fully integrated Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), which limits their ability to offer efficient digital services such as access to e-journals and online databases. Therefore, users may struggle to utilize available resources effectively, reducing the overall quality of the library experience

Statement of the Problem

University libraries in North-West Nigeria face challenges in providing quality services due to inadequate infrastructure, insufficient funding, and limited staff capacity. These challenges hinder the ability of libraries to support academic excellence and meet the information needs of users. As university libraries play a crucial role in supporting their parent institutions' objectives, particularly in the areas of teaching, research, and learning. However, for these libraries to effectively fulfill their mandates, they must continuously assess the quality and availability of their infrastructural facilities for effective services. The assessment process provides an opportunity to evaluate whether these libraries are meeting the expectations of

their parent universities, identifying gaps in their offerings, and determining areas for improvement.

In the North West region of Nigeria, there is a noticeable gap in research that specifically addresses the assessment of Library Infrastructure for Effective Services Delivery by Library Staffs in University Libraries in the North-West Nigeria. Previous studies, both within Nigeria and internationally, have focused on related topics but have not adequately addressed the unique challenges facing libraries in this region. Rapid advancements in information and communication technologies (ICTs) further complicate this issue, as libraries must now contend with expensive digital facilities, sophisticated tools, and the need for users to possess ICT skills to fully utilize available services.

Additionally, limited funding and technological infrastructure in North West Nigerian universities may hinder the effective use of these resources by both staff and students. Thus, it is essential to investigate the current state of these libraries to determine how well they are equipped to serve their communities, how their facilities are being utilized by library staffs, and what improvements are necessary to align with modern demands.

The problem this study seeks to address is the lack of comprehensive assessment of Library Infrastructure for Effective Services Delivery by Library Staffs in University Libraries in the North-West Nigeria. Without such evaluation, it is difficult to determine how these libraries contribute to their parent institutions and where they fall short in providing necessary tools for academic success. This study will explore whether the existing facilities are sufficient, how effectively they are being used, and what additional measures are needed to ensure that these libraries remain relevant and capable of supporting the educational missions of their universities.

Research Objectives

1. To assess the current state of library infrastructure in university libraries in North-West Nigeria.
2. To evaluate the impact of library infrastructure on services delivery by library staffs in university libraries in North-West Nigeria.

Methodology

The study employed a descriptive survey research design, which is appropriate for gathering detailed information regarding the Appraisal of Library Infrastructure for Effective Services Delivery by Library Staffs in University Libraries in the North-West Nigeria. This design was chosen to enable the researchers to describe and interpret the existing conditions within the libraries in Northwestern Nigeria.

The Study's Population

The research population included Federal University Libraries in the North West; there is a total of seven (7), which served as secondary population, while the primary population involved all the University Librarians, and library staffs. The data collection was carried out using surveys, questionnaires.

Study's Population

S/N	University	No of University Librarian	No Of Library Staff
1	FUDMA	1	127
2	FUG	1	46
3	FUD	1	73
4	UDUS	1	125
5	ABU	1	345
6	BUK	1	251
7	FUBK	1	45
	Total	7	1012

Source: pilot study (2024)

Figure of library staffs

Population of the study

S/N	University	No Of Library Staff	Sample	No. of quest adm	No. of ques returned	%
1	FUDMA	127	12	12	8	67
2	FUG	46	4	4	3	75
3	FUD	73	7	7	4	57
4	UDUS	125	12	12	6	50
5	ABU	345	34	34	22	65
6	BUK	251	25	25	18	72
7	FUBK	45	4	4	2	50

Total	1012	98	98	63	64
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Figure of Response Rate

Analysis of Questionnaires Distribution and Return

The table presents the distribution and return of questionnaires across seven universities in North-West Nigeria. A total of 98 questionnaires were administered, and 63 were returned, representing a response rate of 64%. **Response Rate by University**

The response rate varies across universities:

FUDMA: 67% (8/12) FUG: 75% (3/4) FUD: 57% (4/7) UDUS: 50% (6/12) ABU: 65% (22/34) BUK: 72% (18/25) FUBK: 50% (2/4). The overall response rate of 64% indicates a moderate level of participation. The response rates across universities suggest varying levels of engagement, with FUG having the highest response rate (75%) and UDUS and FUBK having the lowest (50%).

Data analysis

The current state of library infrastructure in university libraries in North-West Nigeria

S/N	Items	Yes	%	No	%
1	Library Buildings and Facilities	Yes	%	No	%
A	Are the condition of the library building is standard?	13	20.6%	50	79.4%
B	Are the library facilities (e.g., seating, shelving, study areas) adequate?	15	23.8%	48	76.2%
C	Is the library accessible to users with disabilities?	8	12.7%	55	87.3%
2	Technology and Equipment	Yes	%	No	%

a	Are the library's computer systems and software up-to-date?	17	27%	46	73%
b	Are there sufficient computers and internet access for users?	8	12.7%	55	87.3%
c	Are there any other technologies (e.g., printers, scanners) available in the library?	26	41.3%	37	58.7%
3	Lighting, Ventilation, and Security	Yes	%	No	%
A	Are the lighting in the library adequate?	2	3.2%	61	96.8%
B	Is the ventilation system in the library adequate?	14	22.2%	49	77.8%
C	3. Are there adequate security measures in place to protect library materials and users?	21	33.3%	42	66.7%

The study reveals that the majority of respondents indicate that the library building condition, facilities, and accessibility for users with disabilities are not adequate. Most of the respondents report that computer systems and software are not up-to-date, and there is a lack of sufficient computers and internet access. Lighting is a major issue, with almost all respondents indicating it is inadequate. Ventilation and security measures also have significant concerns. The findings suggest that university libraries in North-West Nigeria face substantial challenges in providing adequate infrastructure to support learning and research. impact of library infrastructure on services delivery by library staffs in university libraries in North-West Nigeria

Impact of library infrastructure on services delivery by library staffs in university libraries in North-West Nigeria

S/N	Items	Yes	%	No	%
1	Library Infrastructure	Yes	%	No	%
A	How would you rate the impact of library infrastructure (e.g., buildings, technology, facilities) on your ability to deliver services?	13	20.6%	50	79.4%
B	Which aspects of library infrastructure do you think have the most significant impact on services delivery? (Select all that apply)	Yes	%	No	%
i	Buildings and facilities	50	79.4%	13	20.6%
ii	Technology and equipment	54	85.7%	9	1.4%
iii	Lighting and ventilation	56	88.9%	7	11.1%
iv	Security measures	45	71.4%	11	17.5%
2	Services Delivery	Yes	%	No	%

a	How would you rate the quality of services you deliver to users?	23	36.5%	40	63.5%
b	Which services are most affected by the state of library infrastructure? (Select all that apply)	13	20.6%	50	79.4%
I	Reference services	54	85.7%	9	1.4%
ii	Circulation services	43	68.3%	20	31.7%
iii	Research assistance	23	36.5%	40	63.5%
iv	User education	57	90.5%	6	9.5%
4	Section D: Staff Perspective	Yes	%	No	%
5	Do you think adequate library infrastructure would improve your ability to deliver quality services?	62	98.4%	1	1.6%

The study reveals that most the respondents believe that library infrastructure significantly impacts services delivery ,with lighting and ventilation, technology and equipment, and buildings and facilities being key areas .it was reveals that the quality of services delivered is perceived as un satisfactory by most respondents ,with user education, reference services, and circulation services being most affected. Almost all the respondents agree that adequate library infrastructure would improve services delivery.

Conclusion

The study reveals significant challenges in university libraries' infrastructure in North-West Nigeria, impacting services delivery and user satisfaction. Key areas of concern include library buildings and facilities, technology and equipment, lighting, ventilation, and security. The findings suggest that inadequate infrastructure hinders the delivery of quality services, affecting user education, reference services, and circulation services. Conclusively shows that university libraries in North-West Nigeria face significant infrastructure challenges, impacting services delivery and user satisfaction. The findings highlight the need for investment in library infrastructure, prioritization of development, and staff training to support academic excellence.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations are proposed for implementation to hence the challenges faced the university libraries under study

1. Invest in library infrastructure: Prioritize development of library buildings, facilities, technology, and equipment to support learning and research. Allocate funds to improve library buildings, facilities, technology, and equipment.
2. Improve lighting and ventilation: Address lighting and ventilation issues to create a conducive study environment.
3. Enhance accessibility: Ensure library facilities are accessible to users with disabilities.

4. Provide staff training and support: Equip library staff with necessary skills to maximize benefits of improved infrastructure.

5. Regular assessment and evaluation: Conduct regular assessments to identify areas for improvement and ensure library infrastructure meets user needs:

By implementing these recommendations, university libraries can enhance services delivery, support academic excellence, and improve user satisfaction.

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